

THE TERM OF FOLKLORE AND CONDITIONS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF FOLKLORE AND ETHNOGRAPHIC ENSEMBLES

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In the Uzbek folk art, a unique system of visual means of expression, different from fiction, has been developed. The vividness of symbolic images, constant adjectives, traditional formulas in these folk songs is evident in the abundance of caressing and diminutive additions, parallelism, and the active and unique use of idioms in the language of folklore works.

Folklore is a collective creation. The works of folk art are created and live in a long-term creative process, passing from mouth to mouth, from generation to generation, from teacher to student. The author and the time of writing of the literary sample will be clear and known. The uncertainty - anonymity of the author of folklore works (Greek *anonymis* - unknown) does not deny that the work was once created by an individual creator.) As V. G. Belinsky said, folklore "does not have famous names, because its author is always the people. No one knows who weaved his simple and simple songs that silently and clearly describe the internal and external life of a modern people or tribe... and this song is passed from clan to clan, from generation to generation, and time passes. it changes with time: sometimes they shorten it, sometimes they lengthen it, sometimes they compose it anew, sometimes they add other songs to it, sometimes they weave another song in addition to it - then the song turns out to be an epic, only the people he can consider himself the author... Literature is a different work: now it is not the people, but individual persons who reflect various aspects of the people's life in their practical activities. In literature, a person appears with a tula, and literary stages are always distinguished by the names of persons. We see that a folklore work "once woven by an unknown person (individual) becomes an example of collective creativity in the process of passing from mouth to mouth, from generation to generation. Enjoying the creative potential of the collective, it is perfected and acquires ideological and artistic maturity.

It is appropriate to say that folklore was created in ancient times as a mass creation of the collective, and its first examples were intended for collective performance. At that time, the individual creator had not yet fully separated from the collective. With the improvement of socio-political relations, the growth of people's aesthetic thinking, and the deepening of the division of labor, individual performers - singers, storytellers, entertainers, entertainers, and halfas - began to

shine with their skills. But these talents are also guided by the people's ingenuity and perform works that have been passed down from mouth to mouth, from generation to generation, from teacher to student, and of course, in the process, they add something from themselves and use their personal skills. was showing. Tila old woman, Sultan old woman, Jolmon Bakhshi, Boron poet, Jumanbulbul, Jossok, Khonimjon Khalfa, Bibi poet, Suyav Bakhshi, Amin Bakhshi, Yoldosh nightingale, Sultanmurad, Kurbanbek, Khidir poet, Yoldosh poet, Suyar poet, Sherna Yuz Bashi, Mulla Kholnazar, Haibat Soki, Kunduz Soki, Fazil Yoldosh son, Ergash Jumanbulbul son, Polkan Jonmurad son, Islam Nazar son, Saidmurad The son of Panoh, the poet Abdullah, the poet Umir, the son of Nurmon Abduvoy, the son of Kholyor Abdukarim, the son of Bola Bakhshi, the son of Kadir Rahim, and others, thanks to their individual performances, passed down the works created with the collective genius. passed down to the generation. Some of them started to create by themselves, relying firmly on the traditions of this collective creativity, more precisely, they did not remain at the level of traditional epic singers, but were able to rise from performance to the level of creativity.

Folklore is an oral creation. The way of living and creation of oral folk art has its own importance. Because it was created as a representative of the way of life, worldview and belief, struggle and defeats of our ancestors in the distant past, when writing was not yet discovered. According to the folklorist scientist A.A. Potebnya, folklore is born from the "source of memory", more precisely, from the passing of memory from mouth to mouth. He said that the "source of memory" is not just the concept of one or several people, but the words, rumors, and oral opinion of the whole people. This rumor or verbal opinion is passed from teacher to student (father to child), from generation to generation, from generation to generation, and lives on, polished by the spirit of the new era, the potential of a new performer and creator. Such polishing is manifested in the introduction of some changes to the form and content of this or that folklore work - something is seen, something is left out. For example, a historical fact may be omitted from the work due to forgetfulness. Or, due to the forgetting of the song part of the epic, it can live in the form of a fairy tale, or on the contrary, a fairy tale can grow into an epic. These are characteristic features of the way of life of folklore as a live process of oral creativity. Folklore lives through word of mouth, while fiction lives through writing. Folklore works are told orally (tales, proverbs, riddles, narratives, legends, anecdotes, praises, etc.) and sung (songs). Fiction is only read.

No matter how the form and content of a folklore work changes due to word of mouth, this does not reduce its ideological-artistic and social-aesthetic value,

because it reflects the attitude of the creative people to reality. The main reason why folklore works have been passed down from mouth to mouth for many centuries is that traditionalism is one of the unique features of folklore, which determines its ideological and aesthetic essence. Traditionalism in folk art does not mean only the relative stability of the text of this or that work in the process of word-of-mouth transmission, but also the characteristics, form and form, expressive means and heroes of the original performance of that work in the process of passing from generation to generation. also means that it has remained relatively unchanged.

Tradition is a product of collective creativity, and at the same time, it is a unique form of collective preservation of folklore works. Oral creativity is an invariable form of folklore, which, in turn, means to memorize and remember. Among the Uzbek bakhshi poets, the presence of improvisers who know how many terms, sing and weave more than 40 traditional epics is a result of this traditional need. After all, traditionalism is a distinctive feature not only of folklore, but also of folk music, dance and applied art.

Traditionalism has its socio-historical sources, the first samples of folklore were created in the primitive society, they reflected the relatively settled customs and views on life of the people of that time. This situation ensured that the form, plot, images and motives of folklore works gained a certain stability.

The people have an artistic taste - an aesthetic taste that has been formed over the centuries, and folklore always follows this folk aesthetic principle. This is an objective law for folklore. The impact of socio-economic development on folk aesthetics drives traditionalism in folklore. For example, as a result of the fundamental changes made in the people's beliefs by the development of social thinking, the genres of badik, kinna, burey-burey, as well as "Sust xotin", "Choi momo", "Barot keldi" ceremonies have taken a wide place in the social life of the population. By this time, the tradition of creating epics began to decline, and genres such as songs, proverbs, stories, and oral stories continued, and some new genres, including historical songs, appeared. Also, the motifs in the traditional song have changed, they have been replaced by images and views that match the content of the new event.

Serious changes took place in the poetic system of some genres. In particular, in the new epics born in that period, although they rely on the epic, ready-made patterns, and motifs typical of traditional epics, they are no longer based on unnaturalness, as in traditional epics, but on life reality and objectivity. was expressed as If the ideal heroes of traditional epics win by acting with the help of

supernatural forces, the heroes of new epics are real historical figures who act and achieve their goals based on the reality of that time. Such a difference can be seen in the example of the conflict between traditional epics and new epics. In traditional epics, the conflict arises on the basis of the requirements of individual interests, and in new epics, the need for public interests arises. Therefore, the conflict of new epics has a vital basis and its solution is also realistic.

Variation in folklore. Examples of folk art live only in different versions during the live performance. Variability is the lifestyle of folklore. Variability is a feature arising from the nature of folklore, its creation and the laws of living in live oral creativity, and it fully covers the plot, imagery, poetics, and genre features of folklore works. Therefore, a variant is a different copy of a certain work that arose in the context of a living oral epic tradition, which can live side by side without denying each other and differ from each other. For example, there are thirty-three complete and fragmentary versions of the "Alpomish" epic written by twenty-eight epic writers. Among the people, there are many more options.

An important feature of variability is that it exists within the form. Consequently, appearance is essentially a somewhat broad phenomenon, which is a plot and a genre of folk poetic creation, which are sharply different from each other in terms of the ideological concept advanced in the work, as well as the composition of the work and the means of artistic representation. consists of samples. By the way, there are Uzbek, Karakalpak, Kazakh and other forms of the "Alpomish" epic. A certain epic can have several forms even in one nation. For example, the epics "Alpomish", "Shirin bilan Shakar" and "Sahibqiron" are spread among the Uzbek people in two versions.

Thus, variability determines the popularity, popularity and distribution limits of folklore works, provides rich material for determining the causes of changes in folklore, revealing the underlying laws of past and current processes in folk art. Folklore works are created on the basis of a unique realistic method, which differs from the method in written literature in that it overgeneralizes reality, exaggerates the hero, does not detail his personal life, does not show psychological complexity, and typifies it in the harmony of a fantastic image.

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